

GENDER ISSUES IN ANTHROPOCENTRIC PROVERBS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the anthropocentric features of English and Uzbek proverbs about men and women and the issue of gender in them. Also, this article presents the most famous proverbs in the two languages and the work done by scientists on them. When we studied proverbs in English and Uzbek, we found out the differences and similarities between them.

Key words: *gender, paradigm, proverb, genderlinguistics, phraseology, mental and cognitive processes*

Proverbs are one of the main criteria that show the cultural and spiritual life of every nation, its thoughts and conclusions. They reflect the long past, experiences and legends of that nation that are preserved in the memory of the people. Also, proverbs are the wisdom of the people. and shows his conclusions based on his experiences in history. English and Uzbek proverbs have similar characteristics, they are the result of centuries of observations, in other words, proverbs are the cream of wisdom.

Deeper analysis of proverbs and finding their differences and alternatives between different languages is an important issue of modern linguistics. We know that phraseological units in each language have their own characteristics. When learning, he first compares such units in his own language to other language units. Finding the differences and similarities of phraseological units, whether it is a proverb or a phrase, is the biggest help in learning the language more deeply. will be Proverbs are one of the main criteria that show the cultural and spiritual life of every nation, its thoughts and conclusions. They reflect the long past, experiences and legends of that nation that are preserved in the memory of the people. Also, proverbs are the wisdom of the people. and shows his conclusions based on his experiences in history. English and Uzbek

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When it comes to proverbs about men and women in English and Uzbek languages, the issue of gender is the main issue in both languages, and they also have different aspects. Because these two languages were formed under different historical, social and economic conditions. And we should analyze these proverbs from the point of view of anthropocentrism and the issue of gender.

First of all, if we emphasize the issue of anthropocentrism and gender, these concepts are considered one of the main concepts of modern linguistics today. There are paradigms with special characteristics in each layer of the language system. Paradigm (lat. *parádeigma* - *paradeigma*) as a methodological concept was introduced into scientific use by the American philosopher Thomas Kuhn in the last quarter of the century. The scientist used this term in his book "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" published in 1962 to explain "leaps" in science. "Paradigm" is a clear philosophical and methodological concept for every linguist.

At the end of the 20th century, a new paradigm, anthropocentrism, entered linguistics. Because language is for society, its importance is seen in the mental and cognitive processes of the human psyche, and finally, language performs the function of a tool in mass communication.

In addition, in anthropocentric proverbs, gender, i.e. sex, has a special place. Gender linguistics is developing as one of the modern trends in linguistics. Gender linguistics, which studies processes related to the role of man and woman in society, their mental world, and the social and cultural characteristics of language, is becoming

important in modern linguistics. The concept of gender is included in the science as a concept indicating the difference between biological sex, that is, male and female. From a social point of view, this concept is a concept that shows the role of men and women in society.

If we explain the gender interpretation in anthropocentric proverbs in English and Uzbek languages, in these two languages, a man is the economic provider of the family, and a woman is a person responsible for its social and spiritual environment. We can see this in the example of the following proverbs:

Man makes houses, woman makes homes.

Men get wealth, woman keep it.

They are as following in Uzbek :

Ayol so‘m qilar,erkak chaqa.

Yomon er to‘y buzar,yomon xotin uy.

Also in Uzbek language the proverb "Erni er qiladigan ham xotin,qaro yer qiladigan ham xotin" may alter to the proverb "A good husband makes a good wife" yoki "A good Jack makes a good Jill".

In addition, the upbringing of children in the family, especially the upbringing of girls, is entrusted to women in both national cultures. If we pay attention to the following proverbs, we can clearly see this:

As is the mother, so is her daughter - Onasini ko‘rib qizini ol.

But there is also a form of proverbs with this meaning that indicates the responsibility of both men and women in English:

Like mother,like daughter. - Like father, like son.

If we look at the issue of gender, in proverbs based on the concepts of community management, wisdom and wisdom, it is mainly given by the word "man". We will consider this in the following examples:

The wit of one man, the wisdom of many.

The healthful man can give counsel to the sick.

What’s a man but his mind?

In the land of blind, the one-eyed man is king.

There are proverbs like that in Uzbek language also :

Arslon izidan qaytmaydi, yigit so‘zidan.

Yomon o‘g‘il - molga o‘rtoq,

Yaxshi og‘il jonga.

Also, in proverbs based on the concepts of appearance, beauty and youth, we can see mainly women and girls in both languages. For example, in English they are as follows:

A man is old as he feels, a woman is as old as she looks.

As an equivalent of this proverb, we can take the following proverb in Uzbek language:

Ayoldan yoshini so‘rama, erkakdan maoshini.

Another notable aspect is that some anthropocentric proverbs in English have alternatives in Uzbek without male or female characters or with animal names:

A dog is man’s best friend - It vafo, xotin jafo.

A hungry man is an angry man - Ochdan qoch.

The coat makes the man - Kurakka libos, eshakka to‘qim.

The man in boots doesn’t know the man in shoes- Tani boshqa dard bilmas.

In conclusion, English and Uzbek anthropocentric proverbs have several differences and similarities in terms of gender. In a world where knowledge of foreign languages is the need of the hour, learning proverbs and using them to decorate our conversation takes language learners to another high level.

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